

Ricgraph: showcasing research in context using Pure and other sources

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What if... we look at research information as a graph?

- We have relations between objects
- We can “walk” from one object to another
- Related objects are neighbors
- No duplicates

Object = person, organization,
article, book, dataset, software, ...

What if... we are able to harvest any source we'd like?

We can collect information that is:

- of specific interest (and not more)
- only visible in our own organization
- not harvested by other sources

Sources = Pure, Yoda data repository, Research Software Directory, OpenAlex,
UU staff pages, Zenodo, GitHub, NWO grant application system, Scopus,
OpenAIRE, ...

What is Ricgraph?

- A **graph** that can represent any object (node) that has a relation (edge) to another object
- It can **harvest** information from several sources
- Stores **metadata**, not objects
- **Research in context**: people, organizations, research outputs, skills, projects, ... in relation to each other
- A graph is **fast**
[time to access a neighbor not dependent on number of nodes in graph]

Research output = article, book, dataset, software, ...

Sources = Pure, Yoda, Research Software Directory, OpenAlex, UU staff pages, Zenodo, GitHub, NWO grant application system, Scopus, OpenAIRE, ...

Ricgraph sources (example for Utrecht University)

can contain information about any organization

information only accessible at UU

Ricgraph

information open to public

Pure UU

Yoda data repository

UU staff pages skills

OpenAlex UU publications

OpenAlex UMCU publications

Research Software Directory UU

What can you do with Ricgraph?

Answers to questions like:

- What are the research outputs of a person?
- Who has contributed to a research output?
- With whom has a person worked?
- What research outputs have two persons in common?
- What identifiers does a person have?
- Visual inspection.

Research output = article, book, dataset, software, ...

Identifier = ORCID, ISNI, SCOPUS_ID, email, name, GitHub, Twitter, ...

Everything in one graph

- person
- article
- data set
- software

Add any entity you'd like

E.g. projects, skills

- person
- article
- data set
- software
- skill
- project

What can Ricgraph do?

What are the research outputs of person A?

- person
- article
- data set
- software

What can Ricgraph do?

Who has contributed to research output C?

- person
- article
- data set
- software

What can Ricgraph do?

With whom has person A worked?

- person
- article
- data set
- software

What can Ricgraph do?

What research outputs have person A and person B in common?

- person
- article
- data set
- software

What can Ricgraph do?

What identifiers does a person have?

What can Ricgraph do?

Visual inspection: (some) persons and publications of

- OpenAlex Utrecht University
- OpenAlex University Medical Center Utrecht

Some lessons learned

- Without identifiers we are nowhere
- We need to be able to resolve any identifier to any other
- I think only one preferred identifier will not work
- A graph is the way to go! 😊

You can install and use Ricgraph yourself!

Identifier = ORCID, ISNI, SCOPUS_ID, email, name, GitHub, Twitter, ...

Questions?

- Demo? Ask Arjan Sieverink!

Links

- GitHub (software, documentation and videos): <https://github.com/UtrechtUniversity/ricgraph>
- Research Software Directory: <https://research-software-directory.org/software/ricgraph>
- Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7524314>

More information, presentations, demos, install workshops:

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